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PRIORITY TASKS FOR IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL AND MANAGEMENT MECHANISMS FOR THE FORMATION OF SOCIAL CREATIVITY IN FUTURE EDUCATIONAL MANAGERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14512082>

Abstract: In this article, the theoretical and methodological foundations of improving the organizational and management mechanisms for the formation of social creativity in future educational managers and the tasks of forming social creativity in future educational managers are studied based on advanced foreign experiences. Also, theoretical aspects of the formation of social creativity in future educational managers were analyzed.

Key words: principle, mechanism, improvement, theoretical-methodological basis, international standards, academic, marketing, management, integration, forecasting, globalization, functional, manager, social creativity, modernization, authoritarian, liberal-democratic, scientific-organizational, conceptual-pedagogical, hierarchical.

INTRODUCTION. In the new stage of societal development, higher education plays a crucial role in the activities of individuals, particularly in the training of future specialists and qualified personnel. One of the important tasks of higher education is to train highly qualified, competitive professionals that meet the demands of the labor market. Educational institutions in our country have recognized the necessity of joining the Bologna Convention, and some processes in this direction have already begun. Along with structural changes in higher education institutions, disciplines and practical activities that promote the development of intellectual and creative competencies are being developed for future specialists. The most important priority task is to train students to be individuals with critical thinking and intellectual depth. In Uzbekistan, the issue of raising the intellectual potential of students and shaping innovative pedagogical technologies and new approaches is still relevant.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODS. The theoretical and methodological basis for improving the organizational and management mechanisms of social creativity formation in future education managers has been studied and analyzed by Ph. Altbach, K.A. Khoon, R. Shukor, O. Hassan, Z. Saleh, A. Hamzah, R.

Ismail, N.V. Demidova, S.V. Sulima, S.A. Drujilov, K.I. Morozova, S.D. Reznik, S.M. Vasin, O.A. Sazikina, O. Bichkova, L. Verbitskaya, V. Kasevich, M.V. Niyazova, V.YE. Varavenko, G.N. Axunova, B.A. Begalov, A.SH. Bekmurodov, S.S. Gulyamov, Sh.N. Zaynutdinov, M.A. Ikramov, N.K. Yo'ldoshev, I.U. Majidov, D.X. Nabiyeu, R.I. Nurimbetov, B.X. Rakhimov, D.N. Rakhimova, R.A. Rakhmanbayeva, M.Kh. Saidov, A.N. Samadov, T.SH. Shodiyev, Sh.D. Ergashkhodjayeva, A.T. Yusupov, Sh. Qurbonovlar.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. The current stage of societal development sees the education of well-rounded individuals as one of the most important and urgent tasks. In fact, humanism, knowledge, morality, patriotism, the thirst for knowledge, creativity, and striving for innovation hold a leading place in the national values of the Uzbek people. Today, the fact that many of our youth emerge as winners in international competitions, contests, and exhibitions is proof of the strong focus on education and upbringing in our country. Teachers, who are educating the next generation, must be well-versed in modern teaching and educational methods, possess intellectual potential, and have skills in using innovative technologies and information-communication tools effectively. In this context, the following situations emphasize the need to reshape the content and objectives of the future education management specialists' activities based on the application of creative technologies in the educational process:

- First, after our country's independence, the restoration of our great national values, promoting a healthy lifestyle for all citizens, particularly for the youth, was designated as a priority in state policy. As part of this, preparing educators based on global standards and increasing their qualifications in alignment with these demands to cultivate high moral values in youth is an urgent task.

- Second, one of the most important state objectives is to educate morally and physically healthy, mentally developed individuals who can defend the borders of their homeland. This includes improving the education system and training a new generation based on national independence ideas.

- Third, the ongoing reforms in the field of national education, including the transformation of the national education system, reflect a growing tendency in our society to pay greater attention to the upbringing of a healthy and well-rounded generation.

Fourthly, the global process of globalization related to universal technologies has created a social demand for the interpretation of management education within the continuous education system using modern pedagogical

technologies and creative approaches. It is of great importance to update and enrich the content of education and upbringing by shaping social creativity in future education managers. Along with the development of the educational process, the urgent issue that stands before us is to form social creativity in future education managers and achieve efficiency in the physical education of the younger generation. In this context, comparative and analytical study of the historical experiences of the management education system in our country, critically reflecting on practical experiences, and generalizing them will enable us to properly organize the innovative activities of future education management specialists and identify their strategic directions. This necessitates the implementation of targeted pedagogical research.

Shaping social creativity in future education managers, modernizing its organizational and technological foundations, and developing future trends in its development is one of the urgent tasks before the field of pedagogy. The aim of innovative activity is determined by society, and its result is related to the interests of society, directing youth toward social relations, and creating conditions for the realization of natural potential in individuals to gain social experience.

The creative activity of future education managers is based on the continuous organization of the educational process using innovations, which is a process that forms and improves over a certain period of time. The shaping of social creativity in future education managers is expressed in the following aspects:

1. Harmonizing the philosophy of creative activity with management concepts;
2. Mastering pedagogical research methods;
3. Ability to create authorial concepts;
4. Planning and implementing experimental work;
5. Applying the experiences of other researcher-teachers;
6. Collaboration with colleagues;
7. Exchanging ideas and providing methodological support;
8. Preventing and resolving conflicts;
9. Applying innovations to educational management courses and adapting them to specific conditions.

In the process of reforming the content of the education system, the reputation, responsibility, and professional skills of pedagogical staff are steadily increasing in line with state policy. In this regard, the main task is to

renew the activities of teachers and introduce innovations into the educational process. Just like specialists in any other field, the professional preparation level of future managers is evaluated based on their knowledge, skills, competencies, creative potential, and professional suitability, reflected in their unconventional thinking.

The shaping of social creativity in future education managers manifests itself in a creative approach, active creativity, technological and methodological preparedness for introducing innovations, and a new way of thinking in communication culture. During creative activities, innovations and improvements permeate the educational process. Therefore, the introduction of innovations in the educational system is carried out in several stages:

- Analyzing the existing pedagogical issue;
- Designing the planned education system;
- Planning changes and innovations in the pedagogical process, organizing, and monitoring them.

The goal of shaping social creativity in future education managers is to develop teachers' readiness for innovation, their ability to independently work on self-improvement, and enhance their qualifications in organizing lessons and extracurricular activities using modern pedagogical technologies and interactive methods.

There are a number of psychological barriers in shaping social creativity in future education managers. The first of these is the difficulty teachers face in stepping outside their familiar activity boundaries, i.e., the lack of sufficient creativity among teachers. Another reason is that new and unfamiliar things often cause fear and apprehension among people. Therefore, when preparing the new generation of specialists capable of competing, particularly future education management experts, the ability to set future-oriented tasks and solve them, cultivate a high level of intellectual culture, and independently utilize scientific-technical and socio-political information is critical.

CONCLUSION. Today, the intellectual thinking of future specialists is undergoing a transformation, which not only reflects the general moral climate of society but also represents the gradual change in the social identity, spiritual world, goals, and needs of each member of society. Only in this way can a person make a worthy contribution to the formation and improvement of the virtuous qualities of an ideal person, as envisioned by great scholars. In short, equipping our youth with intellectual thinking and creative thought is a demand of the times. The reason for this is that in the modern era, to engage in discussions

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with any competitor or adversary, we must understand their views and ideas more thoroughly, and, if necessary, master them better than they themselves.

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